

ANALYSIS OF THE NON-PENETRATING IMPACT BEHAVIOUR OF CFRP LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

The results of an analytical investigation of the behaviour of CFRP laminates under non-penetrating impact are presented, and compared with experimental results. A continuum model has been developed and implemented in a computer program to predict the global transient response of laminated composite plates. The analytical results have been compared with the experimental force-time traces for two different impactor masses. The agreement between experiment and theory is very good for impact events that do not involve extensive damage. When damage occurs, the predicted forces exceed the values measured. At the moment when damage is observed experimentally, the model predicts the same maximum strain in the fibre direction, for both impactor masses and all energy levels tested.

Keywords: instrumented impact testing, impact damage of CFRP, analytical modelling of impacts

1. INTRODUCTION

There has been considerable research on the impact behaviour of composite materials, especially CFRPs, in the last few years, as seen by the review articles by Abrate [1] and Cantwell and Morton [2]. Theoretical studies have been reported by a number of authors, but most are based on fully numerical approaches such as the finite element method and invariably assume that the force-time history is known. Very few analytical treatments have been presented [e.g. 3-5]. Whereas numerical approaches may be able to capture more of the details of an impact event, analytic solutions are useful for systematic parametric studies and engineering design.

This paper presents the preliminary results of the analytical phase of a combined experimental and analytical study of the non-penetrating impact response of CFRP laminates. The aim of the analytical model is to improve understanding of the parameters that influence impact response and provide a foundation for predicting the onset of impact damage. In the experimental phase of this study, which has been presented elsewhere [6], we have considered

two different ranges of impact velocities using two impactors with a mass ratio of 20:1. The rationale for varying the impactor mass is that the rate at which a structure is loaded affects both its structural response as well as its material behaviour [2]. Therefore, two impact events occurring at the same energy but with different velocities may induce completely different damage states in the target [7-9].

2. REVIEW OF EXPERIMENTS

The experimental results used for comparison in this paper have been reported in full elsewhere [6], and only the salient details are repeated here. The material was a T800H/3900-2 toughened epoxy system, with a fibre tensile strain to failure of 1.6%. The stacking sequence of the 24 ply laminate was $[45/90/-45/0]_{3s}$, with a thickness of 4.65 ± 0.02 mm.

For all tests, a hardened, hemispherical 25.4 mm steel tup was impacted on rectangular test coupons of size 102 mm by 152 mm (4 by 6 inches), which were placed on a steel frame with a 76.2 mm by 127.0 mm (3 by 5 inches) cutout. The test coupons were held in position by adjustable, rubber-tipped toggle clamps. This is essentially a simply supported boundary condition.

The instrumented low mass impacts were performed using a nitrogen gas gun with an instrumented projectile with a mass of 310 g [10]. The instrumented high mass impacts were performed on a drop weight impactor with a 6.14 kg mass. The resulting damage was detected and quantified using C-scan and deply techniques. This provided a complete description of the various damage states consisting of delamination, matrix cracking and fibre breakage.

Figure 1 shows the measured force-displacement curves for static indentation and static deflection of the plate, and two impact events occurring at different velocities but using the same impact energy of 45 J. The static indentation was measured by placing a laminate coupon on a rigid steel plate and indenting it with the impactor nose fixed to the crosshead of a universal testing machine. The static deflection of the plate was measured with the same configuration as in the impact tests.

The impact with the low mass impactor (and thus higher velocity) results in higher contact forces but a lower maximum deflection of the panel compared to the high mass, low velocity impact. These observations were observed consistently over the complete range of impact energies and velocities considered here. The laminate impact response and the resulting damage state as a function of impact velocity are discussed in detail in [6].

The response of the high mass impact (at a velocity of 3.8 m/s) agrees closely with the static flexure test, indicating "quasi-static" behaviour [11]. However, the initial part of the low mass impact curve agrees very closely with the static indentation curve. At this velocity (16.9 m/s) the panel does not have enough time to react quasi-statically. Furthermore, the total impact time decreases by a factor of 4.5, corresponding to the difference in impact velocity ($=\sqrt{20}$).

3. ANALYTICAL MODEL

An analytical model based on the modal superposition technique is being developed and implemented in a computer program, COMPACT, to predict the global transient response of laminated composite plates to impact by non-penetrating rigid projectiles. The following provides a concise description of the current status of this analytical model and its limitations.

The model is applicable to orthotropic rectangular plates and takes into account the combined effects of shear deformation and rotary inertia. Impactor vibrations and damping effects in the laminate have been neglected. A major limitation of the present version of the model is that it does not account for the inelastic behaviour of the laminate caused by damage.

The impact dynamics sub-model assumes the nonlinear Hertzian indentation law for the calculation of contact force F as a function of indentation depth α .

$$F = k \alpha^{3/2} \quad (1)$$

The spring constant k is calculated using the impactor radius and modulus, and the transverse modulus of the plate. For the experiments presented here, $k = 1.19 \cdot 10^9$ N/m^{3/2}. Figure 2 compares the prediction based on Eqn (1) with the measured indentation response of the laminate. Agreement is satisfactory, with a maximum error of 60 μ m in the prediction of indentation depth up to contact forces of 20 kN.

The differential equations of motion are solved for an all-around simply-supported boundary condition using a combination of modal analysis and numerical time integration. The analysis is similar to that presented by Dobyns [3] with the exception that it includes the frequency components arising from cross-sectional rotations of the laminate. It has been found that the present modal analysis required a total of 100 modes for convergence.

Figures 3a and 3b compare the predictions of the contact force-time and laminate deflection-time histories from COMPACT and similar analytical results available from the literature [4]. It should be noted that the authors of Ref [4] assumed a linear indentation law in their analysis.

Analytical contact force-time histories were generated for the various impact conditions used in the experiments reported in [6]. The following section compares the analytical and experimental results.

4. COMPARISON OF ANALYTICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Currently, the analytical model does not predict the onset of damage, and the consequent reduction of panel stiffness. However, by comparing the model prediction with the experimental results, the point of divergence between the curves marks the onset of damage. Calculated values such as stress and strain fields from the model at this instant can be compared for a range of experiments at different velocities, masses, boundary conditions, and so forth, and used to guide the development of criteria for damage onset and growth.

Experimental and analytical results are compared for impact events with incident energy of 9 J in Figures 4a and 4b for low velocity and high velocity tests respectively. There is reasonably good agreement over the complete event, which should be expected as there was no damage observed. For the low velocity test (Fig. 4a), the analysis captures the essential details of the experimental force-time curve, including the initial slope, peak force and impact duration. In the high velocity case (Fig. 4b), the analysis predicts the various oscillations due to the higher modes of plate vibration. Although the time at which the peaks and valleys occur are predicted accurately, the predicted magnitudes are not as close. Nevertheless, the predicted peak force, maximum panel deflection and impact duration correspond closely to the measured values.

Figures 5a and 5b show a similar comparison between experiment and theory at an impact energy of 22 J. From C-scan and deply inspections, it has been established independently that delamination and matrix cracking are the main damage types, with minimal fibre breakage observed in only one panel out of four tested at this level. Inspection of Fig. 5a reveals that at

1.2 ms, the predicted value of the contact force deviates from the experimental value. The model calculates the maximum tensile strain in the panel, in the fibre direction, to be 1.4% at this instant. This is comparable to the failure strain of the T800H fibre (1.6%). It is more difficult to see the onset of damage in the high velocity impact case, as there are a number of oscillations. However, a careful comparison of the experimental curves in Figures 4b (no damage) and 5b (damaged) shows a significant difference in shape of oscillations at 0.45 ms. At this instant, the model predicts a maximum strain in the fibre direction of 1.45%, which is in good agreement with the previous observation for the low velocity impact.

Figures 6a and 6b are the comparison of the force-time curves for an impact energy of 33 J. At this energy level, the model overpredicts significantly the peak force in both low and high velocity impact events. Examination of the test coupons revealed delamination and matrix cracking as well as considerable fibre breakage. At the point where the experimental and analytical curves deviate sharply (about 1.1 ms and 0.3 ms respectively), the model predicts maximum strains in the fibre direction of 1.7% for both impactor masses. The sharp drop in contact force is assumed to be associated with the onset of fibre breakage, whereas a gradual deviation is assumed to be due to matrix damage (Fig. 5a). Since the present elastic analysis overestimates the overall strength and stiffness of the laminate, the predicted impact duration is less than the measured value.

Similar results have been obtained at higher impact energy levels. Figure 7 is a plot of three different candidate parameters to predict the onset of fibre breakage on the back face of the laminate, where the tensile strain is at a maximum. Results are plotted as a function of impact energy and impactor mass. For the high mass impacts, the measured force and panel displacement at the onset of fibre breakage appear to be reasonably constant as a function of impact energy. However, both these values are dependent on laminate stacking sequence, coupon size and other geometric considerations (e.g. shape of impactor nose). Moreover, for the low mass impacts, the measured force at the onset of damage was found to shift considerably along the peaks and valleys of the force-displacement curve from one impact velocity to another. The third parameter is the calculated strain at the back surface of the laminate, in the fibre direction. Not only would one expect this value to be independent of geometric considerations and constant for a given material system, it can be seen in Fig. 7 that it is also the most consistent in value for both masses at all impact energies.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The predicted peak force and impact duration are in good agreement with the experimental results when the incident impact energy is less than the threshold value to initiate damage. Beyond this energy level, the induced internal damage invalidates the linear elastic assumptions of the present version of the model, leading to an over-prediction of the force-time curve.

The onset of measurable damage may be defined as the instant when the analytical and experimental force-time curves deviate. The analysis shows that the maximum strain at the back surface of the laminate, in the fibre direction, is a constant value at this instant, for all energies and velocities tested. This suggests that this parameter may be used to predict analytically the onset of fibre damage during the impact of a laminate of arbitrary stacking sequence and size.

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Fig. 1: Static and dynamic force-displacement curves. The impact tests were carried out at an energy level of 45 J.

Fig. 2: Comparison of static indentation tests and the Hertzian indentation law used in the model.

Fig. 3: Comparison between the predictions of the present model and the analysis of Christoforou and Swanson [4]

Fig. 4: Predicted (thin lines) and experimental force-time histories (thick lines) for high mass and low mass impact at an energy level of 9 J.

Fig. 5: Predicted (thin lines) and experimental force-time histories (thick lines) for high mass and low mass impact at an energy level of 22 J. The arrows indicate the onset of matrix damage.

Fig. 6: Predicted (thin lines) and experimental force-time histories (thick lines) for high mass and low mass impact at an energy level of 33 J. The arrows indicate the onset of severe damage (fibre and matrix damage).

Fig. 7: Measured force, displacement and predicted strain in fibre direction at the onset of severe damage as a function of impact energy, for both impactor masses.